

Detection and characterization of aeolian sand strips on the beach using permanent laser scanning

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Author Contribution Statements

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After consulting relevant resources and checking with the relevant local communities, the authors have confirmed that the lands containing their institutions and all work sites associated with this study do not have cultural or historical significance to a particular indigenous group.

29

Data and code availability

The code for the sand strip detection method, as well as all the scripts used to create the figures in this paper are hosted on <https://github.com/christavanijzendoorn/sandstripdetection>. A snapshot of all code is available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10574283> on Zenodo, as well as a subset of the laser scan data, the moisture content measurements, and the results of the detection method (van IJzendoorn et al., 2024). The results of the detection method in the repository are supplemented with the environmental conditions that were obtained from local Rijkswaterstaat water level stations and KNMI meteorological stations. The full laser scan data set that was collected in Noordwijk between July 2019 and June 2022 is available at <https://doi.org/10.4121/1AAC46FB-7900-4D4C-A099-D2CE354811D2.V1> in the 4TU repository (Vos et al., 2023).

42

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50 Sander Vos reports a relationship with Baars-CIPRO that includes: employment. The other
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GEOMORPHICA

Dutch Abstract for

Detection and characterization of aeolian sand strips on the beach using permanent laser scanning

Detectie en karakterisering van eolische zandstroken op het strand met permanent laser scannen

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Eolische zandstroken zijn ribbels die vaak voorkomen op het strand tijdens harde wind. De zandstroken kunnen over het strand bewegen, wat resulteert in sedimenttransport. Dit sedimenttransport is echter nog niet gekwantificeerd. Permanent laser scannen (PLS) biedt de mogelijkheid om lange termijn en gedetailleerde informatie over zandstroken te verzamelen. Hier presenteren we een methode die zandstroken detecteert in PLS-reflectiebeelden en hun golflengte, oriëntatie en hoogte bepaalt. De detectiemethode wordt toegepast op een maand PLS-data, gemeten met een interval van een uur, op het strand van Noordwijk in Nederland. De gemiddelde golflengte (13 m), hoogte (3 cm) en oriëntatie (onshore-oblique) van de zandstroken die in deze dataset zijn gevonden, komen overeen met eerder onderzoek. Migratiesnelheden worden verkregen door opeenvolgende beelden van zandstrookpatronen te onderzoeken. Met behulp van de tegelijkertijd optredende zandstrookhoogte, wordt vervolgens de sedimenttransport hoeveelheid die optreedt door het verplaatsen van de zandstroken berekend. Tijdens een 8 uur durende transportgebeurtenis wordt een totale sedimentflux van 0.16 m³/m waargenomen, waarvan 0,07 m³/m in landwaartse richting. Daarnaast wordt aangetoond dat de detectiemethode toepasbaar is op andere stranden door drempelwaardes in de methode te kalibreren. Dit opent een nieuwe mogelijkheid in toekomstig onderzoek om PLS te gebruiken om het gedrag en de sedimenttransport hoeveelheden van eolische zandstroken te bestuderen.

Keywords: windgedreven sedimenttransport, ribbels, terrestrisch laser scannen, kustprocessen, Fourier transformatie

1 **Detection and characterization of aeolian** 2 **sand strips on the beach using permanent** 3 **laser scanning**

4 5 **Abstract**

6 Aeolian sand strips are bedforms that often form on the beach during high wind events. The sand
7 strips can move across the beach resulting in sediment transport, but these sediment fluxes have
8 not yet been quantified. Permanent laser scanning (PLS) provides an opportunity to gather long-
9 term and detailed information about sand strips. Here, we present a method that detects sand strips
10 in PLS reflectance images and extracts their wavelength, orientation, and height. The detection
11 method is used on a month-long hourly dataset of Noordwijk beach, the Netherlands. The average
12 sand strip wavelength (13 m), height (3 cm), and orientation (onshore-oblique) found in this dataset
13 are consistent with previous research. Migration rates are obtained by examining successive images
14 of sand strip patterns. Using the concurrent sand strip height, the sediment transport rate
15 associated with sand strips is estimated. During a single 8-hour event, a total sediment flux of 0.16
16 m³/m is observed of which 0.07 m³/m in onshore direction. Furthermore, the detection method is
17 shown to be applicable to other beaches by calibrating its thresholds. This opens a new possibility
18 for future research to use PLS to investigate the behavior and sediment transport rates of aeolian
19 sand strips.

20 **Non-technical Summary**

21 Strong winds blow sand over the beach. This movement of sand can cause waves of lighter and
22 darker sand to show up. These waves are called sand strips. When sand strips move over the beach,
23 the sand that they are made of is moved from one place to another. To measure how much sand the
24 sand strips are moving, we use a laser scanner that gives information about the moistness of the
25 beach and height information in centimeter detail. The laser scanner is put on top of a hotel close to
26 the beach in Noordwijk, the Netherlands. It scans the beach at least once per hour. Since the laser
27 scanner scans so often, we cannot check each scan for sand strips by hand. We have created a
28 method that can automatically tell whether there are sand strips in a laser scan. The method also
29 measures the length and height of the wave patterns. Based on these measurements, we learned
30 that sand strips move an amount of sand that could contribute to dune growth. In the future, the
31 automatic method that we created can be used to search for sand strips in laser scans of other
32 beaches.

33 **Keywords**

34 Aeolian sediment transport, bedforms, terrestrial laser scanning, coastal processes, Fourier
35 transform

36 **1. Introduction**

37 During high wind events on the beach, bedforms with a low amplitude and large wavelength
38 can form (Figure 1). These bedforms are known as aeolian sand strips (Hage et al., 2018a),
39 or alternatively as (wind-ripple) protodunes and early-stage aeolian bedforms (Baddock et
40 al., 2018; Kocurek et al., 1992). Aeolian sand strips commonly form on non-erodible surfaces,
41 such as moist beaches, and start as patches of dry, moving sand that turn into thin strips
42 over time (Delorme et al., 2023; Nield, 2011). Subsequently, sand strips migrate over the

43 bed and can develop towards mature dunes (Baddock et al., 2018; Kocurek et al., 1992).
 44 Sand strips have a wavelength in the order of 10 m and a height in the order of centimeters
 45 (Baddock et al., 2018). Hage et al. (2018a) suggest a threshold velocity for sand strip
 46 occurrence equal to 8 m/s. They also show that the orientation of sand strips is often
 47 alongshore, even with oblique regional winds, implying wind steering by the foredune. They
 48 state that the disappearance of sand strips is mostly caused by the rising tide and suggest
 49 that precipitation can cause a temporary disappearance of sand strips. Since sand strip
 50 formation and development is related to aeolian transport sand strips can be used as an
 51 indicator of aeolian sediment transport occurring on the beach (Hage et al., 2018b).

52 **Figure 1** a) Sand strips on the beach surface in Noordwijk, the Netherlands. b) Point cloud of the beach in
 53 Noordwijk showing sand strip presence due to variations in reflectance. Photo: Kay Boomaars.

54 The migration of bedforms such as ripples can result in creep transport which contributes to
 55 total sediment transport rates. Sherman et al. (2019) quantified the average contribution of
 56 ripple migration to total transport as approximately 3.6%. Thus, ripple migration needs to
 57 be included when calculating total aeolian sediment transport rates, as has been recognized
 58 by, e.g., Uphues et al., (2022); van Rijn & Strypsteen (2020). Like ripples, aeolian sand strips
 59 might make a considerable contribution to total transport rates. However, sediment transport

60 rates associated with sand strip migration are unknown and have not yet been addressed in
 61 the context of total sediment fluxes in a coastal setting. Estimates of ripple migration
 62 transport have previously been made using (Jerolmack et al., 2006; Sherman et al., 2019;
 63 Zhang et al., 2021):

$$q_b = (1 - p)\rho_s u_b H / 2 \quad (1)$$

64 where q_b is the transport rate associated with the bedform, p (-) is the porosity (approx.
 65 0.4), ρ_s is the sediment density (2650 kg/m³ for sand), u_b (m/s) is the migration velocity
 66 of the bedform, H (m) is the ripple height. Application of this equation to sand strips
 67 requires the assumption that sand strips have a triangular shape and requires co-occurring
 68 information about migration speeds and heights.
 69

70
 71 Video monitoring and terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) can be used to study aeolian sediment
 72 transport (Cohn et al., 2022; de Vries et al., 2017; Hage et al., 2018b; Nield & Wiggs, 2011;
 73 Williams et al., 2018) and specifically sand strips (Baddock et al., 2018; Bristow et al., 2022;
 74 Delorme et al., 2023; Hage et al., 2018a; Nield et al., 2011). Sand strips can be tracked in
 75 collected imagery based on the differences in moisture content. In video imagery this is done
 76 based on color values (Figure 1a), where lighter colors indicate drier sand. Laser scans
 77 consist of point clouds that contain (x,y,z)-coordinates as well as a reflectance intensity
 78 value. This reflectance intensity decreases with increasing moisture content (Di Biase et al.,
 79 2021; Jin et al., 2021; Nield & Wiggs, 2011; Smit et al., 2018), which results in similar
 80 patterns as can be seen with the naked eye (Figure 1b). In studying sand strips, TLS has
 81 mostly been used to study individual bedforms (e.g., Baddock et al., 2018; Nield et al., 2011),
 82 whereas video imagery has been used to investigate longer term behavior (Hage et al.,
 83 2018a).

84
 85 Permanent laser scanning (PLS) provides an opportunity to gather long-term and detailed
 86 information about sand strips. Permanent laser scanning uses a laser scanner that is mounted
 87 in the same location and regularly collects scans for periods of weeks to years (Kuschnerus
 88 et al., 2024; Vos et al., 2017). This technique is increasingly used to study coastal processes
 89 (Brodie & Spore, 2015; Cohn et al., 2021, 2022; Hallin et al., 2023; Kuschnerus,
 90 Lindenbergh, et al., 2021; O'Dea et al., 2019; Vos, Anders, Kuschnerus, et al., 2022; Vos et
 91 al., 2020). PLS combines the high spatial detail of TLS with the high temporal detail and long-
 92 term period of data collection that already has been available for video-based methods (e.g.,
 93 Holman & Stanley, 2007). Due to the vertical accuracy in the order of centimeters (Anders
 94 et al., 2021; Kuschnerus et al., 2024), PLS provides the opportunity to study the height of
 95 sand strips over time. This information on the height and therefore volume of sand strips
 96 can, together with their migration speed, result in estimates of the sediment transport rate

97 that is associated with sand strip movement (Equation 1). (Jerolmack et al., 2006; Sherman
98 et al., 2019)

99

100 The aim of this research is to develop a generic method that detects aeolian sand strips in
101 PLS data and extracts the wavelength and orientation of the bedforms, as well as the height.
102 Additionally, we aim to provide an estimate of the sediment transport rate related to sand
103 strip migration. The development of the sand strip detection method is based on a PLS setup
104 in Noordwijk, the Netherlands (Kuschnerus et al., 2024; Vos et al., 2024). The study area
105 and available data, including moisture content samples, are discussed in Section 2. The
106 methods used to pre-process lidar data, detect sand strips, extract their characteristics, and
107 determine accuracy metrics are explained in Section 3. Subsequently, the detection method
108 is applied to a period between 30 January and 28 February 2022. Section 4 presents the
109 output of the detection method in this period. An overview of sand strip characteristics is
110 given and the occurrence of sand strips during different environmental conditions including
111 precipitation is shown, as well as their migration rates. The advantages and limitations of the
112 detection method and its ability to be applied to other PLS datasets are discussed in Section
113 5. Additionally, sand strip characteristics found with the new detection method are compared
114 to previous studies, and an estimation of the sediment flux related to sand strip migration is
115 given.

116

117 **2. Data description**

118 **2.1 Study area**

119 The study site is the beach of Noordwijk aan Zee, the Netherlands ($52.242163^{\circ}\text{N}$,
120 $4.4237101^{\circ}\text{E}$) indicated by the grey dot in Figure 2a. The coastline has an orientation of 30°
121 with respect to the North and faces the North Sea. The beach width depends on the tide and
122 ranges between 100 m and 200 m. Noordwijk has a semi-diurnal tide with a 1 m and a 1.8
123 m tidal range at respectively neap and spring tide (Walstra et al., 2012). The dominant wave
124 direction for waves approaching the Noordwijk coast is southwest (SW) and north-northwest
125 (NNW) (Quartel et al., 2007). The mean wave height along the Dutch coast is 1.2 m and the
126 mean wave period is equal to 5 seconds (Wijnberg & Terwindt, 1995). Furthermore, the wind
127 climate is dominated by winds coming from the southwest (SW) and are thus oblique-
128 alongshore (Figure 2c).

129

130 **Figure 2** a) Location of the field site in Noordwijk (grey dot), along the Dutch coast. Weather stations are
 131 indicated in red, water level stations are indicated in yellow. The inset shows the location of the Riegl VZ-2000
 132 laser scanner (grey dot) and the range it covers (orange rectangle). b) The laser scanner on top of the balcony
 133 of Grand Hotel Huis ter Duin with its corresponding view over the beach. c) The coordinate system of the laser
 134 scans with respect to the laser scanner (grey dot). The orange dots indicate the general extent of each laser
 135 scan. d) The wind direction and wind speeds recorded at IJmuiden during the study period. The radial axis of
 136 the wind rose indicates the number of occurrences in hours and the black line from 30°-210° indicates the local
 137 orientation of the coast.

138

139

140 **2.2 Environmental data**

141 The environmental conditions in the research area are obtained from regional stations. Wind
142 conditions, consisting of both the wind direction (10° intervals, hourly mean) and wind
143 velocity (1 m/s resolution, hourly mean) are collected, as well as precipitation (mm/hr) and
144 tidal data (cm +MSL). The wind conditions are acquired from official Dutch meteorological
145 KNMI station 225 located in IJmuiden at a height of 10 m (Figure 2c), and the precipitation
146 data from KNMI station 215 located in Voorschoten (Figure 2a, red dots). Tidal data is
147 obtained from the Rijkswaterstaat (Ministry of Public Works) water level stations located in
148 Scheveningen and IJmuiden (Figure 2a, yellow dots). As Noordwijk is located in between
149 these stations, the average of these stations is used as the tidal elevation.

150

151 **2.3 Permanent laser scanning (PLS) data**

152 In Noordwijk, a Riegl VZ-2000 laser scanner was mounted on top of Grand Hotel Huis ter
153 Duin (Figures 2a and b). The laser scanner was set up to analyze natural variations at short
154 (hours) to medium (months) time scales for a period of several years. Within the viewing
155 range of the permanent laser scanner (PLS) are the beach, the dunes, the intertidal zone
156 and a beach pavilion (Figure 2b). The PLS covers approximately 1 km in alongshore direction
157 (500 m in both directions), and 300 m in cross-shore direction.

158

159 Due to the known and fixed location and orientation of the PLS, it can obtain point clouds
160 with (x,y,z) -coordinates, and a reflectance value (example in Figure 1b) in a common
161 reference frame. The point clouds are provided in a local Cartesian coordinate system with
162 the origin at the laser scanner location. This coordinate system is translated so the origin of
163 the z-coordinate is at +0 m MSL. The positive x-direction is directed land-inward, resulting
164 in negative x-values at the beach. The positive y-direction is directed north-eastward (NE),
165 parallel to the orientation of the beach. The estimated footprint of each point is 0.09 m^2 on
166 the beach, although this value varies depending on the incidence angle and the distance from
167 the laser scanner. The vertical accuracy of the laser scanner is estimated at around 2 cm,
168 with maximum errors of 3 cm (Kuschnerus, Lindenbergh, et al., 2021). Data gaps in the laser
169 scans occur due to shadow zones caused by obstacles in the range of the laser scanning
170 device such as dunes (upper part) and the beach pavilion (at $x = -180$ and $y = 0$). On the
171 seaward side of the laser scan (lower part of Figure 1b) data gaps are caused by the presence
172 of water.

173

174 The reflectance intensity recorded by the laser scanner in Noordwijk is related to the moisture
175 content on the beach (Di Biase et al., 2021). Thus, the reflectance intensity is used as the

176 basis for sand strip detection. The manufacturer of the laser scanner (Riegl) describes the
177 reflecting intensity as a range-corrected amplitude, internally calculated by the scanner
178 based on the calibration of the manufacturer (Pfennigbauer & Ullrich, 2010). This internally
179 corrected reflectance value is dimensionless and therefore differs from the SI-unit for the
180 target surface reflectance (Vos, Anders, Kuschnerus, et al., 2022). Here, we have assigned
181 the symbol R to the reflectance values produced by the laser scanner. This clarifies the use
182 of the reflectance in any derived units (e.g., Rm^2 in Figure 6).

183

184 The detection method is applied to laser scans from the period of 30 January until 28 February
185 2022. During this period, four storms passed over the Netherlands. The first storm passed
186 on 31 January (storm Corrie). From 16 to 21 February storm conditions occurred for six
187 consecutive days as storms Dudley, Eunice and Franklin passed. For most of the study period,
188 the beach was scanned at an hourly interval. However, the temporal resolution was increased
189 to a scanning interval of 20 minutes from 16 February at 08:40 until 26 February at 23:59
190 (CET, throughout this paper). In total, the laser scanner scanned the beach 1215 times during
191 the complete study period.

192

193 **2.4 Moisture content measurements during sand strip occurrence**

194 To quantify the range of moisture content present in sand strips, sand samples were collected
195 when sand strips were present during windy conditions on 4 February, 17 February (storm
196 Dudley), 18 February (storm Eunice) and 6 April 2022 (Figure 3a). On each sampling day,
197 the crest, windward and leeward sides of multiple sand strips were sampled, as well as the
198 beach surrounding the sand strips, here defined as the trough (Figure 3b). Samples of
199 approximately 150 to 200 grams were collected by scraping the upper 3 mm (± 2 mm) of the
200 sand surface with a small shovel. The samples were oven-dried, and their gravimetric
201 moisture content was determined. Due to sampling errors, loss of moisture during transport
202 and weighing errors, the moisture measurements have a maximum expected error of about
203 10% (for example, moisture content can be expressed as $5 \pm 0.5\%$).

204 **Figure 3** a) GPS locations of sand samples collected on 4, 17, 18 February and 6 April 2022. The main wind
 205 directions during these days are indicated with arrows in the top left corner, and coordinates are in Dutch
 206 Rijksdriehoek system (ESPG:28992). b) Sand sample locations on the trough, leeward side, crest and windward
 207 side of aeolian sand strips. The sand strips are indicated in light yellow and the surrounding beach in yellow.
 208

209 **3. Methodology**

210 **3.1 Overview of detection method**

211 In the field, sand strips are clearly visible due to variations in moisture content (Figure 1a).
 212 If sand strips are present on the beach, the laser scanner reflectance values show a certain
 213 waveform (Figure 1b) with higher (less negative) reflectance values on the sand strip (crest)
 214 compared to the surrounding beach (trough). A similar signal could be visible in the elevation
 215 provided by the laser scanner. However, the expected elevation difference due to the
 216 presence of sand strips is close to the 2–3-centimeter vertical accuracy of the laser scanner
 217 (Kuschnerus et al., 2024; Kuschnerus, Lindenbergh, et al., 2021). Thus, the signal in
 218 reflectance is expected to be stronger than the elevation, and the sand strip detection method
 219 is therefore primarily based on the reflectance.

220

221 The steps that were executed to detect sand strips and extract their characteristics are shown
 222 in Figure 4. Several pre-processing steps were executed on the raw point clouds before
 223 applying the detection method. The area of interest was selected in each scan and a moving
 224 window system was applied to allow for sand strip detection even if sand strips only occurred
 225 in part of the domain. The point cloud in each window was converted into a grid,
 226 subsequently, empty grid cells were interpolated, the grid was detrended and outliers were
 227 removed. The detection of the sand strips was based on the application of a Fourier transform
 228 (e.g., Lefebvre et al., 2011; Van Dijk et al., 2008) that extracts the dominant waveform in

229 the reflectance values (Section 3.4). This detection can be applied in 1D and 2D. The
 230 distinction between these two methods was based on the scan quality by using the amount
 231 of interpolation that was needed in each detection window. The wavelength and orientation
 232 of the sand strips were obtained using the 2D Fourier Transform. If sand strips were detected
 233 in a window based on the reflectance values, a Fourier transform based on the z-coordinates
 234 was applied to determine the height of the sand strips in the window.

235 **Figure 4** Workflow of the sand strip detection method. The three main parts as presented in Section 3.2, 3.3
 236 and 3.4 are shown in grey boxes. Each individual step is shown as an orange cell. Interpolation thresholds are
 237 indicated with diamonds shapes, the light-orange cells are output variables.
 238
 239

240 3.2 Pre-processing of laser scan data

241 3.2.1 Application of a local transformation matrix

242 The laser scanner is subject to movements due to wind forcing resulting in small rotations of
 243 the laser head or of the building on which the scanner is positioned. These small variations
 244 affect the relative alignment of consecutive scans (Kuschnerus, Schröder, et al., 2021;
 245 Soudarissanane et al., 2011). To minimize these alignment errors, time dependent rotation
 246 matrices were calculated and applied. These matrices were obtained by aligning stable
 247 objects in the point cloud. The beach pavilion in front of the hotel and the concrete access

248 path to the beach north of the hotel were used as stable objects. A more detailed explanation
249 for obtaining these matrices is discussed in Vos et al. (2024).

250

251 **3.2.2 Clipping the area of interest**

252 To reduce computation time, each point cloud was clipped to the area of interest. In
253 alongshore direction, the extent of the area of interest was based on the point density. The
254 point density decreases away from the laser scanner with decreasing incidence angle and
255 increasing range (Smit et al., 2018). In this case, point density was not considered sufficient
256 at distances more than 200 m away from the laser scanner in y-direction. Thus, the area of
257 interest was limited to a range of -200 to 200 m in y-direction (Supplementary Material,
258 Figure 1). In cross-shore direction, the area of interest was clipped based on the presence
259 of the dunes and the location of the shoreline. On the landward side, the dunes extended to
260 $x = -150$ m. On the seaward side, the beach width varied with the tidal cycle. Therefore, the
261 shoreline was detected in each scan to determine the seaward limit of the area of interest.
262 Further explanation of the shoreline detection and an example of clipping the area of interest
263 from a laser scan are provided in the Supplementary Material.

264

265 **3.2.3 Filtering based on scan quality**

266 Based on the quality of the point clouds it was decided whether to analyze or disregard them
267 from the analysis. A scan was only analyzed when the following three quality criteria were
268 met: 1) a local transformation matrix was provided with the point cloud, 2) the shoreline was
269 located at $x = -220$ m or further seaward, and 3) at least 1 million data points were available
270 in the area of interest. Reasons for lower quality point clouds include strong wind, high water
271 levels, and reduced visibility during fog or heavy rain.

272

273 **3.3 Pre-processing for the detection of sand strips**

274 **3.3.1 Area selection with a moving window**

275 As sand strips do not necessarily occur at the full beach area, a moving window analysis was
276 applied that allows investigation of the spatial coverage of sand strips in a scan. The applied
277 windows had a fixed window size of 40 m in cross-shore (x) direction and 100 m in longshore
278 (y) direction. In x-direction a step size of 10 m was used and in y-direction a step size of 20
279 m. Thus, the windows overlapped, preventing sand strips from being excluded during
280 detection.

281

282 **3.3.2 Subsampling the data to a grid and interpolating**

283 The data in each window was sampled to a grid, as a grid was needed for the application of
 284 the detection method. To fill gaps in the grid, linear interpolation was applied, and in case of
 285 multiple points in one grid cell the values of these points were averaged. A grid size of 0.40
 286 m was selected based on the estimated laser pulse footprint of 0.09 m² and the percentage
 287 of interpolation needed to create the grid (elaborated in the Supplementary Material).

288

289 Where large gaps in the data are present, interpolation can result in the removal or creation
 290 of sand strip patterns. Thus, windows in which more than 25% of the grid needed
 291 interpolation were disregarded and not further analyzed. Additionally, windows were
 292 disregarded in which more than four alongshore-oriented rows of the grid needed more than
 293 70% interpolation or more than four consecutive alongshore-oriented rows needed more
 294 than 50% interpolation. The effect of interpolation was reduced by limiting the application of
 295 the 1D method to windows with medium interpolation (20% < interp < 25%) and the 2D
 296 method to windows with low interpolation (< 20%). In applying the 2D method, the effect
 297 of interpolation on the detection results was limited by filtering the wavenumbers where large
 298 areas of interpolation are present (as explained in Section 3.4.3).

299

300 **3.3.3 Detrending the grid and removing outliers**

301 The grid in each window was detrended as a dominant 2D linear trend in the reflectance was
 302 present (Figure 5). By detrending the grid, the reflectance variations that occur at meter-
 303 scale stood out more. This increased contrast facilitated the detection of sand strips. The
 304 best-fit trend was found by computing the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse (Soderstrom &
 305 Stewart, 1974) of the grid (Figure 5b). This trend was then subtracted from the original grid
 306 (Figure 5c).

307

308 Subsequently, outliers were removed from the grid. Measurement errors or obstacles present
 309 on the beach (such as persons) induce outliers, leading to difficulties in analyzing the point

310 cloud. A data point was considered an outlier if it had a value smaller or larger than the mean
311 reflectance value of the grid ± 5 times the standard deviation of the detrended window.
312 Outliers were replaced with a value equal to the mean value of the window.

313 **Figure 5** Detrending and removing outliers in a single moving window. a) The original grid, b) the dominant
314 trend in the grid, and c) the grid after detrending and outlier removal. Outliers are indicated with the grey
315 circle. Their visual contrast with the grid has increased in c) but note the reduction of the reflectance scale.
316

317

318 **3.4 Sand strip detection using Fourier transform**

319 Sand strips were detected based on the dominant waveform that is present due to the varying
 320 reflectance values on the bed surface. By applying a fast Fourier transform, FFT, the reflecting
 321 signal of the bed surface was decomposed into different waveforms with their corresponding
 322 wavenumber. The obtained variance density spectrum shows the distribution of the variance
 323 over the wavenumbers that constitute the variation on the bed surface. A large peak in the
 324 spectrum coincides with a strong signal of the corresponding wavenumber. An advantage of
 325 a variance density spectrum is that it provides a complete statistical description of the waves.
 326 The definition is given as

$$327 \quad E(k) = \lim_{\Delta k \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\Delta k} \frac{1}{2} a_m^2 \quad (2)$$

328 with the variance density spectrum $E(k)$, the mean amplitude of the wave-pattern a_m , and
 329 the wavenumber bandwidth Δk (Holthuijsen, 2007). In this case, the wavenumber interval is
 330 dependent on the window length and selected grid size, resulting in a value of 0.025 m^{-2} .

331

332 The variance density spectrum will show a peak at wavenumber k of $E(k)$ if a wave pattern
 333 with wavelength $L (= 1/k)$ is dominant on the bed surface. Based on the height of this spectral
 334 peak and the corresponding wavenumber, sand strips were detected. The height of the peak
 335 was used to distinguish between waveforms at different scales and with different intensities.
 336 Irregularities of $O(\text{cm})$ result in a small spectral peak height at larger wavenumbers.
 337 Gradients that occur on the window scale cause spectral peaks at very low wave numbers.
 338 The applied detrending of the grid significantly reduced the spectral peak of these waveforms
 339 and thereby facilitated the detection of the peak caused by sand strips. The peak of sand
 340 strips is expected to be around $k = 0.083 \text{ m}^{-1}$ in the variance density spectrum, which
 341 corresponds to the average wavelength of 12.0 m of sand strips found by Hage et al. (2018a).

342

343 **3.4.1 Differentiation between the 1D and 2D Fourier detection method**

344 Sand strips were detected by either a 1D or 2D Fourier transform. The 2D Fourier Transform
 345 was applied on windows with high quality data where the required interpolation did not
 346 exceed 20%. The 1D Fourier transform was applied on windows with a required interpolation
 347 between 20% and 25%. In windows where the 2D Fourier transform was applied, the
 348 wavelength and orientation of the sand strips were extracted. The 1D Fourier transform could
 349 have been used to extract the wavelength as well. However, this method does not consider
 350 the orientation of the sand strips, and disregarding the orientation may cause an
 351 overestimation of the wavelength. Therefore, the wavelengths presented in this research are

solely based on the 2D Fourier transform, while the 1D Fourier transform is used for height estimation of the sand strips.

354

The sand strips were detected in both methods depending on a range of possible wavenumbers corresponding to sand strips. A predefined wave number range was applied to exclude wavelengths at which bed forms are not expected to occur. The range of wavelengths considered for the 1D Fourier transform was between 6.67 m and 25.0 m, or alternatively $0.04 < k < 0.15 \text{ m}^{-1}$. For the 2D Fourier transform this range was stricter with a wavelength ranging between 8.00 m and 18.18 m, or alternatively $0.056 < k < 0.125 \text{ m}^{-1}$. These initial ranges were based on wavelengths found by Hage et al. (2018a).

362

3.4.2 Sand strip detection using a 1D Fourier transform

For the detection of sand strips with the 1D FFT method, five lines in y-direction were drawn through each window. The reflectance values along the lines were stored. A reflectance profile of one of these lines is shown in Figure 6. From each of these reflectance profiles, the variance density spectrum was calculated (Figure 6c). From this spectrum the largest spectral peak was selected. Based on all wave numbers that are smaller than this peak wave number (orange line in Figure 6c), a wave pattern was created with the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) (orange line in Figure 6b).

Figure 6 The 1D Fourier transform detection method. a) The detrended reflectance grid of a window where sand strips are present. b) The reflectance profile (grey) along the white transect in a) and its IFFT approximation (orange). c) The variance density spectrum of the original profile (grey) and the spectrum in which wave numbers larger than the peak are removed (orange). This reduced spectrum is the basis for the IFFT approximation in b).

376

The IFFT approximation was compared to the original reflectance profile using the root mean square error (RMSE). It was assumed that the Fourier approximation coincided with the original reflectance profile when the RMSE was below 0.5. Then, the wavenumber corresponding to the spectral peak was assumed as the wavenumber of the reflectance

381 profile. If the RMSE was above 0.5, the next highest peak in the spectrum was considered,
 382 and again the profile was approached with the IFFT until the RMSE criterion was met. Sand
 383 strip occurrence was determined for a line if the matching peak height (with a RMSE < 0.5)
 384 exceeded 10 R²m and the corresponding wave number was in the range of 0.04 < k < 0.15
 385 m⁻¹. Subsequently, sand strip occurrence in the window was assumed if at least four out of
 386 the five profile lines indicated their presence.

387 388 **3.4.3 Sand strip detection using a 2D Fourier transform**

389 For the detection of sand strips with the 2D FFT method, the reflectance signal of the bed
 390 surface (Figure 7a) was decomposed into waveforms in both x- and y-direction, which
 391 resulted in two-dimensional variance density spectra (Figure 7b). The energy in the variance
 392 density spectra corresponding to wavenumbers outside of the range of 0.125 < k < 0.056
 393 m⁻¹ were removed (white area in Figure 7b). Subsequently, significant peaks in both the k_x
 394 and k_y distribution were determined (Figure 7c and d). Peaks in the distribution curves were
 395 considered significant if the peak height exceeded 3/4 of the maximum height of the
 396 distribution curve and if the prominence (Kirmse & De Ferranti, 2017) exceeded at least 1/3.
 397 Sand strip occurrence in a window was indicated if a significant k_x and k_y peak were found
 398 and the total energy in the remaining variance density spectrum exceeded 1000 (R²m)².

399 **Figure 7** The 2D Fourier transform detection method. a) The detrended reflectance grid of a window where
 400 sand strips are present. The grey arrow indicates the extracted sand strip orientation. b) The 2D variance
 401 density spectrum with in white the excluded wave number range. c) The energy distribution along the wave
 402 numbers in x-direction. d) The energy distribution along the wave numbers in y-direction. In both c) and d)
 403 the detected significant peaks are indicated with a dashed grey line (peak max).
 404

405 When irregular sand strips are present, a 2D pattern occurs that may result in the detection
 406 of multiple significant wavenumber peaks (in either x- or y-direction). The number of peaks
 407 determines the modality of the distribution curve. A unimodal distribution only contains one
 408 peak, a bimodal distribution contains two peaks and a multimodal distribution multiple. For
 409 each window, the modality was recorded during the detection method. Only unimodal sand
 410 strip patterns were considered in the analysis of the sand strip characteristics.

411

412 When cells that need to be interpolated are not evenly spread over the window, i.e., due to
 413 data gaps, sand strip occurrence may wrongly be indicated. This occurs because the data
 414 gaps can cause the energy in the spectrum for low-valued k_y 's to increase, initiating a total
 415 energy above the detection threshold. By excluding these low-valued k_y 's, the spectral energy
 416 decreases significantly, preventing the detection of these pseudo-sand strips. For example,
 417 k_y values below 0.01 were removed from the wavenumber range of interest if the required
 418 interpolation along the x-axis was above 20% for a width of at least 2 m. In cases where
 419 more interpolation was required, a larger range of low-valued k_y 's was removed. An additional
 420 threshold ($k_y < 0.04$) was set for cases where most interpolation occurred in the first or last
 421 quarter of each window. This distribution indicates that the window may have been at the
 422 edge of the beach surface which could lead to the erroneous detection of sand strips.

423

424 **3.4.4 Determination of wavelength and orientation with the 2D Fourier transform**

425 In windows where sand strips were detected with the 2D FFT method, the wavelength and
 426 orientation of the sand strips were determined (Figure 7a and b). The detected significant k_x
 427 and k_y peaks (Figure 7c and d) were used to calculate the resultant wave number:

$$428 \quad k = \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} \quad (3)$$

429 The resultant wave number is directly related to the wavelength of the sand strips ($L = 1/k$).
 430 This assumes that smaller and larger wave patterns outside of the detected wave number
 431 peaks are not related to the presence of sand strips. In windows with multiple detected
 432 significant peaks, the maximum k_x and k_y peaks and the minimum k_x and k_y peaks were
 433 recorded and used to calculate the wavelength. However, these wavelengths were not
 434 included in the analysis of the sand strip characteristics.

435 The orientation of the sand strips was calculated based on the following equation:

$$436 \quad \theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_y}{k_x} \right) \quad (4)$$

437 This orientation is expressed in degrees relative to the x-axis (cross-shore). Where needed,
 438 these values are converted to an orientation with respect to the North. The accuracy of the
 439 wavelength and orientation are governed by the bandwidths of k_x and k_y . The bandwidths of
 440 the wavenumber domain in the Fourier transform are $\Delta k_x = 0.025 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $\Delta k_y = 0.010 \text{ m}^{-1}$
 441 at a window size of 40 m by 100 m in x- and y-direction.

442

443 3.4.5 Height determination of detected sand strips using a 1D Fourier transform

444 If sand strips were detected in a window, either with the 1D or 2D FFT method, the height
 445 of the sand strips was determined with a 1D Fourier transform based on the bed surface
 446 elevation. The elevation grid required additional detrending compared to the reflectance grid
 447 (compare Figures 7a and 8a), so the method was limited to the 1D Fourier Transform which
 448 made further detrending more straightforward to implement. The height determination was
 449 comparable to the 1D detection method based on reflectance. However, the focus was on the
 450 height of the spectral peak rather than the wavenumber of the peak. Like the pre-processing
 451 steps in Section 3.3, the point cloud with z-coordinates was gridded in each detection
 452 window, the grid was detrended and outliers were removed. Five lines were drawn through
 453 each window (one line shown in Figure 8a) and the z-coordinates along these lines were
 454 stored.

455

456 Despite the detrending of the elevation grid, the elevation profiles can still contain a slope.
 457 Thus, a third polynomial best fit (orange line in Figure 8b) was subtracted from each elevation
 458 profile (grey line in Figure 8b). This resulted in detrended profiles (grey line in Figure 8c)
 459 from which the variance density spectrum could be obtained. Like the 1D detection (Section
 460 3.4.2), an IFFT was applied, based on the wavenumbers lower than the highest spectral
 461 peak, to approach the detrended elevation profile (orange line in Figure 8c). An IFFT
 462 approximation profile was assumed to be representative for the elevation profile when the
 463 RMSE was below 0.02 m. If the RMSE was above 0.02 m, the next highest peak in the
 464 spectrum was considered, and again the profile was approached with the IFFT until the RMSE-
 465 criterion was met.

466 **Figure 8** Sand strip height determination with a 1D Fourier transform. a) The detrended elevation grid of a
 467 window where sand strips are present. b) The original elevation profile (grey) along the white transect in a) and
 468 its fitted trend (orange). c) The detrended elevation profile (grey) and its IFFT approximation (orange). This
 469 reduced spectrum is the basis for the IFFT approximation in b). The resulting sand strip elevation is 6.8 cm.

470

471 The height of the sand strips was assumed to be represented by the variance density value
 472 of highest spectral peak in the variance density spectrum that meets the RMSE-criterion. The
 473 underlying physical assumption is that sand strips are the most distinct and energetic
 474 waveform present, resulting in a high and narrow spectral peak. This assumption can be
 475 made because there is a clear distinction between sand strips and other bedforms and shapes
 476 on the beach (Nield, 2011). Additionally, several filtering steps were executed to ensure that
 477 no pseudo sand strips are present in the scans (Sections 3.3.2 and 3.4.3). In turn, the
 478 amplitude is calculated by reversing Equation 2 and assuming that $H = 2 a_m$:

$$479 \quad H = 2 \sqrt{2 E(k) \Delta k} \quad (5)$$

480 This calculation assumes a symmetrical, sinusoidal simplification of the bedforms, where in
 481 practice the bedforms are peaked and slightly asymmetrical. This results in conservative
 482 estimates of the height and, in turn, sediment transport rates. Since only the spectral peak
 483 height and no additional spectral information was used for the height calculation, it should
 484 be noted that the IFFT approximations visualized in, e.g., Figures 8 and 14 are not necessarily
 485 representative for the calculated height.

486

487 In Figure 8 the height calculation resulted in a sand strip height of 6.8 cm. Note that the
 488 wavelength ($L = 20$ m) that was found based on the elevation (Figure 8c) is equal to that
 489 based on the reflectance (Figure 6b and accounting for the orientation in Figure 7b), which
 490 shows the compatibility of the different methods.

491

492 **3.5 Detection accuracy metrics**

493 The accuracy of the detection method was examined by determining the occurrence of false
 494 positives (FP) and false negatives (FN) with a visual validation. A false positive was indicated
 495 when sand strips were found by the detection method, but they were not visually present in
 496 the reflectance of the bed surface. A false negative was indicated when no sand strips were
 497 found by the detection method, but they were visually present in the reflectance of the bed
 498 surface. The determination of false positives and negatives was executed in a time-based
 499 and area-based manner. Firstly, all 72 scans that were collected on 23 February 2022 were
 500 analyzed. For each separate scan, it was determined whether the detection method correctly
 501 indicated the presence of sand strips at that moment in time. Otherwise, a time-based false
 502 positive or negative was assigned to the scan. Secondly, 18 scans (30 January at 11:00,
 503 18:00, 18.53, 20:00 and 23:00, 5 February at 09:00, 13 February at 22:00, 14 February at
 504 11:00, 15 February at 12:13, 16 February at 05:00 and 13:00, 21 February at 04:00 and
 505 16:00, 23 February at 13:20 and 22:20, 26 February at 00:40, 06:00 and 08:40) were
 506 randomly selected and the coverage was calculated of windows in which sand strips were
 507 detected. This area with detected sand strips was compared to the areas in which sand strips

508 were and were not visually present. This resulted in an area-based percentage of false
509 positives and negatives. The counted occurrence of false positives and negatives was
510 converted into percentages for the time-based and area-based methods using the total
511 amount of scans and the area covered by all windows, respectively.

512

513 **3.6 Analysis of temporal and spatially varying sand strip characteristics**

514 Comparing sand strip occurrence to the environmental conditions was done based on scans
515 where the 2D or the 1D method could be applied. The analysis of the wavelength, orientation
516 and height were based on scans in which the 2D method could be applied. The average
517 wavelength, height and orientation of each scan is used in the analysis rather than multiple
518 values of these shape properties for one scan. Each scan contains around 150 windows due
519 to the moving window, where the exact number of windows is governed by the beach width.

520

521 **3.7 Determination of sand strip migration rates**

522 A single high-wind event with high quality data and long-term presence of aeolian sand strips
523 was selected to analyze the migration rates of aeolian sand strips. Specifically, scans from
524 23 February at 22:00 to 24 February at 06:00 were used to extract the migration rates. The
525 applied approach was adapted from Hage et al. (2018a). In each scan, lines were drawn in
526 the direction of the wind. The lines were drawn in two boxes, one north and one south of the
527 beach pavilion. In each box, multiple lines were drawn at a 6-meter cross-shore interval.
528 Having several parallel lines in the cross-shore allows for the determination of cross-shore
529 variations in the migration rates of sand strips. Along each of the lines, the movement of the
530 sand strips was measured manually by tracking the location of the reflectance peaks between
531 scans. The migration rate per time step is determined based on the change in location of the
532 sand strip crests and the known time interval between the scans. For each line, the calculated
533 migration rates for all time steps are averaged, resulting in a mean migration rate per drawn
534 line.

535

536 **4. Results**

537 **4.1 Detection output and accuracy**

538 Application of the sand strip detection method in the period between 30 January 2022 until
539 28 February 2022 (Figure 9) resulted in the identification of sand strips in 261 out of 1215
540 scans (27.7%). In 72 scans, sand strips were detected with the 1D Fourier transform, and in
541 the other 189 scans sand strips were detected with the 2D method. Low quality data caused
542 272 scans (22.4%) not to be analyzed. Low quality data might have been caused by
543 unfavorable environmental conditions, as especially during the storm period between 16 and

544 22 February these types of scans occurred. Based on visual validation, it was determined
 545 that the maximum percentage of either false positives or false negatives was no more than
 546 4% (Table 1). False negatives could have occurred because the detection method was not
 547 applied in areas with considerable interpolation, whereas these areas were included in the
 548 visual validation. False positives were mostly detected in cases where the sand strips were
 549 oriented within 15° of the shore normal direction. Since sand strips with this orientation were
 550 not observed during the visual validation, they are considered false positives and are
 551 disregarded in the analysis.

552
 553 **Figure 9** The output of the sand strip detection method in the study period.

554
 555 **Table 1** Percentage of time-based and area-based false positives and negatives. The time-based percentages
 556 were calculated based on 72 scans collected on 23 February 2022. The area-based percentages were calculated
 557 based on 18 random scans.

	Time-based	Area-based
False negative	3.6 %	3.8 %
False positive	3.9 %	3.4 %

558 559 **4.2 Overview of sand strip characteristics**

560 **4.2.1 Moisture content**

561 The in-situ moisture content measurements (Figure 10) show a considerable difference in
 562 moisture content between the sand strips and the surrounding beach. The sand strips have
 563 a moisture content of around 2 to 3%, while the surrounding beach (represented by the
 564 trough) has a moisture content of around 8 to 10%. This difference is much larger than the
 565 estimated error of the moisture measurements (Section 2.4). The threshold between the
 566 moisture content of the sand strips and the surrounding beach seems to be around a value
 567 of 6%.

568
569 **Figure 10** Measurements of moisture content across aeolian sand strips.
570

571 **4.2.2 Height, wavelength, and orientation**

572 The height of the detected sand strips varies between 1.4 cm and 8.5 cm, with most sand
573 strips having a height in the range between 2.0 and 4.0 cm (Figure 11a). The distribution of
574 the detected heights is positively skewed, where the tail of the distribution is on the right-
575 hand side of the curve. The mean height of the sand strips is equal to 2.8 cm. The wavelength
576 of the detected sand strips varies between 8.9 m and 17.6 m. The distribution is relatively
577 symmetrical and has a mean wavelength of 13.2 m with a standard deviation of 1.5 m (Figure
578 11b). The orientation of the detected sand strips (Figure 11c) varies from 338° to 91° with
579 respect to north, and from 29° to 142° with respect to shore normal. The mean orientation
580 is equal to 75° with respect to shore normal, which indicates that most sand strips are
581 directed alongshore oblique at a 15° angle from the beach (black line in Figure 11c).

582
583 **Figure 11** a) height, b) wavelength, and c) orientation of detected sand strips. In c) the black line indicates the
584 alongshore beach orientation, the red line indicates the shore normal, and the radial axis represents the count
585 (i.e., number of scans).
586

587 **4.3 The environmental conditions for sand strip development**588 **4.3.1 Wind direction**

589 The formation, development, and disappearance of aeolian sand strips is governed by
 590 environmental conditions such as wind direction, wind velocity, tide, and precipitation (Figure
 591 12). Throughout the study period, the wind mainly came from the southwest (Figure 2c)
 592 corresponding to values around 215° (Figure 12a). Wind events coming from the west to
 593 northwest ($270\text{--}315^\circ$) also occurred, but less often. Sand strips mostly appeared during
 594 south-westerly winds ($210\text{--}240^\circ$), corresponding to alongshore to slightly oblique alongshore
 595 winds (Figure 12a and Figure 13a). Wind events coming from inland (wind direction $< 180^\circ$),
 596 for example at the end of February, did not lead to sand strip development. Oblique onshore
 597 winds coming from the west to northwest (wind direction $> 270^\circ$), only a few times led to
 598 sand strip development.

599

600 **Figure 12** The occurrence of sand strips under different environmental conditions during the study period. a)
 601 wind direction, where the horizontal dashed line indicates that orientation of the beach (210°). b) wind velocity,
 602 where the horizontal dashed lines at 8 m/s and 10 m/s respectively indicate the minimum wind speed for sand
 603 strip occurrence and formation. c) precipitation and d) tide.

604

605 The orientation of the sand strips is mostly parallel to the wind direction (Figure 13b). The
 606 median angle of the difference between the wind and sand strip orientation is equal to 20°.
 607 A difference > 45° occurred only 14 times. These large differences occurred during
 608 alongshore winds ($\leq 240^\circ$, $n=9$) and during onshore oblique winds ($> 240^\circ$, $n=5$). In the
 609 study period, alongshore winds occurred 157 times and onshore oblique winds 24 times.
 610 Thus, an angle > 45° between the wind direction and the orientation of the sand strips is
 611 more common for onshore-oblique winds than for alongshore winds.

612

613 **Figure 13** a) Wind speed and direction when sand strips are detected, b) wind direction plotted against the
 614 difference in angle between the wind direction and the sand strip orientation.

615

616 4.3.2 Wind velocity

617 The wind speed during the study period ranged between 2 m/s and 26 m/s (Figure 2c and
 618 Figure 12b). In the period between 16 and 23 February several high wind events occurred.
 619 During high wind events, many scans were deemed bad quality data which means the sand
 620 strip detection method was not applied. Scans in which sand strips were detected occurred
 621 during wind velocities between 7.0 m/s and 24 m/s (Figure 12b and 13a). Sand strip
 622 occurrence only happened once out of 27 times that a wind speed of 7 m/s was measured,
 623 whereas sand strip occurrence was more common (20.5%) for a wind speed of 8 m/s. Thus,
 624 the minimum wind velocity related to sand strip occurrence for this study period and field
 625 site is around 8 m/s.

626

627 The minimum wind velocity related to sand strip formation is larger than that related to sand
 628 strip occurrence. Sand strip formation is considered the first detection of sand strips in a
 629 scan after at least 3 consecutive scans of good quality. The requirement for good quality
 630 scans is included since otherwise formation may have occurred during bad quality scans. In
 631 total, there are 20 formation events according to this definition, although 3 of these formation
 632 events are disregarded since the disappearance and reappearance of sand strips may have

633 been related to precipitation (Section 4.3.4). For the remaining 17 formation events, the
634 sand strip formation occurs between a minimum and maximum velocity of respectively 10
635 and 16 m/s.

636

637 **4.3.3 Tide**

638 Sand strips mostly formed during falling tide and mostly disappeared during rising tide.
639 Specifically, 60% of the sand strip formations occurred during falling tide and 24% during
640 low tides (Figure 12c). The timing of sand strip formation during the falling tide varied.
641 Sometimes sand strips formed at the beginning of falling tide, while other times they formed
642 just before low water. Sand strip disappearance mostly occurred during rising tide (47%).
643 The disappearance during rising tide is mostly after low water, at the beginning of rising tide.
644 However, sand strips survived rising and high tide 7 times, which indicates that sand strips
645 do not necessarily disappear during these phases of the tidal cycle.

646

647 **4.3.4 Precipitation**

648 Sand strips are detected during some precipitation events, while they are not detected during
649 others (Figure 12d). During the precipitation event of 4 February, sand strips were detected
650 in two consecutive scans prior to the precipitation peak, and during the precipitation peak of
651 4.9 mm/h. The sand strips were no longer detected after the precipitation peak, coinciding
652 with an abrupt increase in the wind direction from 220° to 320° (i.e., from alongshore towards
653 shore-normal wind). Similarly, sand strips were detected during and after a precipitation
654 event on 15 February (from 13:00 to 22:00). However, during other precipitation events,
655 sand strips are not detected during the peak of precipitation. During precipitation events on
656 30 January, 16 February and 20 February, sand strips were not detected despite their
657 detection in three consecutive scans before precipitation started. On 16 February and 20
658 February, sand strips were detected again within one hour after the precipitation stopped.

659

660 For the precipitation event of 16 February, a comparison is made between two windows
661 before and during the precipitation peak at 05:00 and 06:00 (Figure 14a). At 05:00, sand
662 strips were detected based on the reflectance values (Figure 14b and c). At 06:00, the
663 precipitation intensity was equal to 18 mm/h. The variations in reflectance that were present
664 before the precipitation disappeared during this precipitation (Figure 14 b and e). As a result,
665 no sand strips were detected at 06:00 based on the reflectance values (Figure 14e and f).
666 However, there were variations in height present before the precipitation (Figure 14d) that
667 remained present during the precipitation (Figure 14g). These height variations allowed a 1D
668 Fourier transform to be applied on the z-coordinate. The height of the sand strips detected

669 at 05:00 and 06:00 were similar (i.e., 2.7 and 2.8 cm). This indicates that the same sand
 670 strips were present before and during the precipitation peak, which indicates that
 671 precipitation did not cause their disappearance. Although not shown, similar behavior
 672 occurred during the precipitation event on 20 February.

673

674 **Figure 14** The presence of aeolian sand strips on 16 February before and during precipitation. a) time series of
 675 precipitation with orange dots indicating scans with detected sand strips and the grey dots scans without. The
 676 vertical dashed line indicates the precipitation peak at 06:00. b) reflectance grids at 05:00. c) reflectance and
 677 d) elevation profile along the white line in b). e) reflectance grid at 06:00. f) reflectance and g) elevation profile
 678 along the white profile in e).

679

680 **4.4 Cross-shore varying sand strip migration rates**

681 Migration rates were analyzed for the period between 23 February at 22:00 and 24 February
 682 at 06:00. The wind had an alongshore direction in the analyzed period (black arrow in Figure
 683 15), resulting in sand strips moving in the same direction. Migration rates were analyzed
 684 based on 8 lines in a box downwind of the beach pavilion (grey box in Figure 15) and 10 lines
 685 in a box upwind of the beach pavilion (orange box in Figure 15). The migration rates vary
 686 over the width of the beach and decrease in landward direction (Figure 15b). The maximum
 687 migration rate was equal to 3.3 m/h, occurring at $x = -237$ m upwind from the beach club
 688 (orange box). The minimum measured migration rate is equal to 0.3 m/h. The mean
 689 migration rate is equal to 1.3 m/h. Furthermore, the migration rate and the beach width are
 690 correlated with $r = 0.69$, implying an increase in migration rate towards the waterline. The

691 migration rates occurring downwind of the beach pavilion show larger deviations from this
 692 trend, which might be related to the effect of the beach pavilion on the downwind wind field.

693

694 **Figure 15** a) Laser scan on 24 February 2022 at 03:00 with two boxes in which the migration velocities of the
 695 aeolian sand strips were determined for the period between 23 February 2022 at 22:00 and 24 February at
 696 06:00. The wind direction in this period is shown with the black arrow. b) Cross-shore variation in migration
 697 rates. The color of the dots corresponds to the boxes in a).

698

699 5. Discussion

700 5.1 Advantages and limitations of the sand strip detection method

701 Sand strips can successfully be detected, and their characteristics can consistently be
 702 extracted by applying a Fourier transform based method to permanent laser scanning data.
 703 Laser scan data from Noordwijk beach in the Netherlands, in the period from 30 January until
 704 28 February 2022, was used to evaluate the detection method. Low quality data (22% of
 705 available scans) can prevent the application of the detection method. Bad quality data
 706 occurred most often during high wind speeds, aligning with previous findings of Kuschnerus,
 707 Schröder, et al. (2021). This is a weakness in the application of the detection method since
 708 sand strips are more likely to occur during these types of conditions. In the scans of sufficient
 709 quality, false positives and false negatives occurred no more than 4% of the time. The
 710 extensive time series of laser scanning that is available at Noordwijk can provide detailed
 711 information about short term and long-term development of sand strips. Additionally, since
 712 the detection method is based on a moving window approach, detailed studies of the spatial
 713 distribution of sand strip occurrence and their characteristics can be conducted in the future.

714

715 Currently, the successful application of the sand strip detection method is dependent on
 716 distinguishing moisture variations on the beach from the reflectance intensity recorded in the
 717 laser scans. For this beach, the moisture content threshold between the relatively dry sand
 718 strips and wet surrounding beach lay around 6%. During times of precipitation, these
 719 moisture variations diminish which makes the reflection-based method incapable of detecting
 720 sand strips. A Fourier transform based on height differences is able to detect sand strips

721 during precipitation events. Thus, we recommend applying an elevation-based detection
722 method during precipitation events, which can reduce the occurrence of false negatives.
723 Alternatively, the use of a height-only detection method can be explored, although this would
724 probably require detailed detrending of the elevation grid (see Section 3.4.5). Another future
725 improvement of the method would be to include a consistent method to extract migration
726 velocities. The values reported in this research were extracted manually, but cross-spectral
727 techniques (e.g., Lee et al., 2021; Van Dijk & Lindenbergh, 2017) could be used to automate
728 this procedure.

729

730 An additional limitation to the detection method is the extraction of the sand strip height.
731 Currently, this height is determined based on the peak of the spectrum (Section 3.4.5). By
732 selecting the peak, sand strips are assumed to be uniform and sinusoidal, and it is assumed
733 that noise and topographic variations that are not related to sand strips are discarded. In
734 general, this assumption may be applicable since sand strips have a waveform that is distinct
735 from other shapes on the beach (Nield, 2011), resulting in a strong, narrow peak in the
736 spectral signal. However, the results in Figure 14d and g show that this assumption might
737 not be valid for scans with strong spatial variations. Visually, these bedforms seem higher
738 than the estimate that was based on the spectral peak (estimate of 2.7 cm vs. maximum
739 peaks of approx. 5 cm). In the future, using a wider wave number range may provide a
740 better height representation for sand strips with peaked and asymmetric crests.

741

742 **5.2 The applicability of the method on other sandy beaches**

743 The detection method presented in this research was developed based on a single study site
744 and a specific permanent laser scanning system. Other laser scanning systems may have
745 different settings and units for recording the reflectance intensity. Additionally, environmental
746 factors and scene specific measurement geometry is expected to affect the relation between
747 the surface moisture content and the reflectance intensity (Nield et al., 2014). This results
748 in different calibration curves between surface moisture content and reflectance intensity per
749 system and location (Di Biase et al., 2021; Jin et al., 2021; Nield et al., 2011, 2014; Smit et
750 al., 2018). When applying the detection method, the difference in these calibration curves
751 may result in different densities in the variance density spectrum. This indicates that the
752 different thresholds that were used in this research would need to be altered to detect sand
753 strips for different locations.

754

755 For example, the detection method is applied to a point cloud of the beach at Mariakerke-
756 Bad (near Oostende, Belgium) collected on 16 January 2018 (Brand et al., 2019; Vos, Anders,

757 De Wulf, et al., 2022). Small adjustments were made to the window size to accommodate
 758 for the different beach geometry. Initially, the method does not detect the sand strips present
 759 on the beach (Figure 16a). The window that contains sand strips (Figure 16b) results in a
 760 variance density spectrum (Figure 16c) that has a total energy of $860 (R^2m)^2$ which is below
 761 the detection threshold determined for Noordwijk at $1000 (R^2m)^2$. However, the sand strip
 762 orientation based on the significant energy peak in the spectrum correctly represents the
 763 sand strips in Mariakerke-Bad (gray arrow, Figure 16b). In this case, lowering the threshold
 764 for the peak spectral energy may result in the accurate detection of the sand strips in this
 765 scan. Thus, the sand strip detection method is applicable to other sandy beaches provided
 766 that the thresholds used in the sand strip detection are calibrated to the specific field location.

767

768 **Figure 16** a) Point cloud of 16 January 2018 at 22:00 in Mariakerke-Bad. No sand strips are automatically
 769 detected in this scan despite their presence in the upper right corner of the domain. b) Analyzed window with
 770 sand strips. c) The variance density spectrum extracted from the window in b). The sum of the variance density
 771 in this spectrum is below the detection threshold, but the significant peak in the spectrum (grey dot) results in
 772 a realistic wavelength and orientation (grey arrow in b).

773

774 **5.3 Comparison of extracted sand strip characteristics to previous studies**

775 The sand strip detection method can extract several characteristics such as height,
 776 wavelength, and orientation. Additionally, it provides information on the environmental
 777 conditions during which sand strips occur. The detection method resulted in a unique dataset
 778 that describes the height of sand strips in 261 scans throughout a month-long period.
 779 Previously, only the height of singular sand strips was reported. For example, Baddock et al.
 780 (2018) measured a sand strip with a height of 6 cm. Similarly, Uphues et al., (2022) and van
 781 IJzendoorn et al. (2022) observed erosion/deposition patterns in the order of centimeters
 782 that may have been related to the presence of aeolian sand strips. These descriptions match
 783 the sand strip heights measured in this study. Namely, the sand strip detection method
 784 determined a mean height of 2.8 cm with most sand strips falling within a range of 2 to 4
 785 cm.

786

787 The sand strip detection resulted in a mean wavelength of 13.2 m (standard deviation = 1.5
788 m). Hage et al. (2018a) observed sand strips on a similar beach with a mean wavelength of
789 12.0 m (standard deviation = 2.8 m). The larger standard deviation compared to this study
790 could be related to the method of extracting the wavelength which was done with a 1D
791 method applied on alongshore lines. On the other hand, most extracted wavelengths in this
792 study were determined using a 2D method that considers the orientation of the sand strips.
793 Additionally, a predefined wavelength-range ($8.00 < L < 18.18$ m) was used in this study
794 based on the 95% confidence interval found by Hage et al. This resulted in limited detectable
795 wavelengths in this study. However, the range seems to not have excluded any sand strips
796 since the detected sand strips had a smaller wavelength-range ($8.9 < L < 17.6$ m, Section
797 3.4.1) than the predefined range and followed a Gaussian distribution.

798

799 The mean orientation of the sand strips detected in this study was alongshore to oblique-
800 alongshore with a mean angle of 15° from the alongshore beach orientation. This is in
801 correspondence to the observed orientation by Hage et al. (2018a), who noted that sand
802 strips mostly were oriented within 30° of the shoreline. They also note that onshore-oblique
803 winds can result in alongshore sand strips indicating topographic steering by the steep
804 foredune (Bauer et al., 2012; de Winter et al., 2020). These trends are further quantified in
805 this study, showing that differences in the angle between the wind direction and sand strip
806 orientation of $> 45^\circ$ are more likely to occur during onshore-oblique wind events compared
807 to alongshore winds.

808

809 The minimum wind velocity related to sand strip occurrence is 8 m/s, which matches the
810 threshold found by Hage et al. (2018a). However, the wind speeds that occurred during sand
811 strip formation in this study were slightly higher (10-16 m/s). Baddock et al. (2018)
812 measured the development of a protodune at wind speeds of 5.5 to 6.5 m/s, which would
813 indicate a much lower velocity threshold. Their study took place in drier conditions (5% vs
814 1.5%) and on a beach with a finer grain size (300 vs 237 μm). Thus, beach characteristics
815 such as grain size (Field & Pelletier, 2018; Hallin, Almström, et al., 2019; van IJzendoorn et
816 al., 2023) and moisture content (Chepil, 1956; Davidson-Arnott et al., 2008; Wiggs et al.,
817 2004) seem to have a major influence on the velocity threshold for sand strip formation, as
818 they have on aeolian sand transport in general. Only on comparable beaches, the velocity
819 threshold for sand strip formation is the same, indicating that a threshold based on the shear
820 velocity as available for aeolian ripples (Sherman et al., 2019; Uphues et al., 2022) might be
821 more suitable.

822

823 Hage et al. (2018a) related sand strip disappearance to 1) rising tides, 2) precipitation and
824 3) surface drying and suggested that sand strips disappear temporarily during precipitation
825 events. In this study, sand strips most often disappeared during rising tides (47%). Based
826 on the height-based detection method it was shown that sand strips do not disappear during
827 precipitation events (Figure 14). The artificial disappearance is caused by the dependence of
828 reflectance-based detection methods on variations in moisture content. During precipitation
829 events these differences in moisture content decrease, but the morphology of sand strips
830 stays intact. Similarly, surface drying can reduce moisture variations on the beach (Nield et
831 al., 2011). Future research could apply a height-based detection method to sand strips
832 occurring in dry periods to determine whether surface drying results in the disappearance of
833 sand strips. Additionally, future investigations may determine whether sand strips can
834 migrate during precipitation or if they become inactive due to a reduction in aeolian transport.

835

836 Sand strip migration velocities found in this study range between 0.3 and 3.3 m/h, with a
837 mean migration velocity of 1.3 m/h. The mean migration velocity confirms the value of 1.24
838 m/h found by Hage et al. (2018a) but is much higher than the velocity of 0.176 m/h found
839 by Nield et al. (2011). This difference may be associated with lower migration velocities found
840 in recently formed bedforms.

841

842 Our measurements show a decreasing trend in the migration velocity towards the dune toe.
843 The migration velocity of aeolian sand strips is weakly dependent on the wind velocity, given
844 that the threshold velocity is exceeded (Hage et al., 2018a; Kocurek et al., 2010). The wind
845 velocity and shear velocity decrease in landward direction (Bauer et al., 2009; Walker et al.,
846 2006), which results in lower sediment transport rates (Bauer et al., 2012; Davidson-Arnott
847 et al., 2008) and, subsequently, might explain the decreasing migration rate. Additionally,
848 wind velocities are affected by objects, resulting in irregular wind patterns downwind of the
849 obstacle (Nordstrom & McCluskey, 1984; Poppema et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2017). This
850 disturbance might cause the cross-shore decreasing trend in migration velocity to be less
851 clear downwind of an obstacle (i.e., beach pavilion).

852

853 **5.4 Estimating the transport rates associated with aeolian sand strip migration**

854 The combination of detailed height measurements and migration rates allows for an estimate
855 of sediment transport rates associated with aeolian sand strip migration. Assuming sand
856 strips have a triangular shape, Equation 1 which has previously been used for ripple transport
857 (Jerolmack et al., 2006; Sherman et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021) can be applied. Since the
858 sand strip height was determined using a sinusoidal signal, the heights and associated

859 sediment transport rates are conservative. Using a mean migration velocity of 1.3 m/h and
860 a mean bedform height of 0.03 m, the average transport rate during the sand strip event on
861 23/24 February is estimated to be 0.009 kg/m/s or 0.020 m³/m/h.

862

863 Sand strip migration can contribute to sediment fluxes in the beach-dune system. Dune
864 growth rates along the coast in Noordwijk are up to 10-12 m³/m/yr (Vos et al., 2024). During
865 the 8-hour event on February 23/24 approximately 0.16 m³/m sand moved in the form of
866 sand strips. The average orientation of the sand strips during the event was 64 degrees with
867 respect to shore-normal. Following the cosine-rule (Bauer & Davidson-Arnott, 2002), this
868 results in a cross-shore sediment flux of 0.07 m³/m. Thus, sand strip migration during this
869 single event was associated with cross-shore transport volumes that correspond to 0.58-
870 0.70% of total dune volume growth at Noordwijk beach. If several of these events occur per
871 year, transport rates associated with sand strips might contribute considerably to the amount
872 of dune growth. However, anthropogenic impacts like buildings (Vos et al., 2024) and
873 bulldozing (Barbero-García et al., 2023) may make it difficult to discern the contribution of
874 sand strips to long-term dune evolution on an urbanized beach like the one in Noordwijk.
875 Additionally, aeolian sand strips might contribute considerably to subaerial alongshore
876 transport. This could be especially important for locations with unimodal wind climates and
877 restrictive boundaries such as jetties and headlands (Hallin, Huisman, et al., 2019; Miot da
878 Silva et al., 2012). Overall, the estimated transport rates associated with sand strips fall in
879 line with other studies indicating the relevance of bedforms to morphological change, both
880 above water (Sherman et al., 2019; Uphues et al., 2022) and underwater (Aagaard et al.,
881 2001; Jones & Traykovski, 2019; Wengrove et al., 2022).

882

883 **6. Conclusions**

884 A sand strip detection method suitable for permanent laser scanning data was developed.
885 The method was applied to a dataset collected from 30 January to 28 February 2022 on the
886 coast of Noordwijk, the Netherlands. The method can be applied to other sandy beaches after
887 calibrating the thresholds used in the sand strip detection. The detection method indicates
888 sand strip presence and extracts characteristics such as wavelength, orientation, and height.
889 Measurements of average wavelength (13 m), orientation (onshore-oblique), height (2.8
890 cm), and migration rates (1.3 m/h) match previously reported sand strip characteristics. By
891 detecting sand strips based on elevation instead of reflectance, it was shown that sand strip
892 morphology remains intact during precipitation events. An estimate of aeolian sediment
893 transport rates associated with sand strips can be made using measurements of sand strip
894 height and migration velocity. A total sediment flux of 0.16 m³/m in the direction of sand

895 strip migration was observed during an 8-hour event in the study period. Thus, transport
896 rates associated with sand strips may have a considerable contribution to subaerial sediment
897 fluxes. This stresses the relevance of sand strips for morphological change on the beach.

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GEOMORPHICA

Supplementary Materials for

Detection and characterization of aeolian sand strips on the beach using permanent laser scanning

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As one of the pre-processing steps of the laser scan data (Section 3.2), the area of interest is clipped from each laser scan (Section 3.2.2). In alongshore direction, the point density determines the extent of the area of interest. In cross-shore direction, the dunes determine the landward extent of the area of interest at $x = -150$ m and the shoreline determines the seaward extent. The shoreline is detected per scan based on the presence of points along cross-shore profile lines that are drawn every 20 m. All points within 0.15 m distance of each cross-shore profile line are recorded. When the point density seaward of $x = -200$ along the profile line is relatively high (i.e., > 20 points), the most seaward point is marked as the shoreline location along that line. When the point density along the profile line is relatively small (i.e., < 20 points), the median location of the points along the profile line is marked as the shoreline location. Ultimately, the median location of all shoreline locations is selected and used as the seaward extent of the area of interest. Figure 1 shows an example of the clipping of the area of interest from a laser scan.

Figure S1.

Overview of the clipping workflow that is based on the alongshore point density and the cross-shore location of the shoreline. a) Point cloud of the beach with a horizontal line at $x = -210$ m (grey) where the alongshore point coverage is best. b) The reflectance values of all points that are within 0.20 m of the line at $x = -210$ m. Boundaries are drawn at $y = 200$ and -200 m, as the point density deteriorates beyond these lines. c) Cross-shore profile lines are drawn every 20 m and for each line the most seaward point is indicated (orange dots). The shoreline location (horizontal black line) is set at the median location of all seaward points. The clipped area of interest is present within the black lines.

As part of the pre-processing for the detection of sand strips (Section 3.3), the point cloud in each window is sampled to a grid (Section 3.3.2). The optimal grid size was selected based on the footprint size of the laser pulse and the percentage of interpolation needed to create the grid. The estimated footprint was 0.09 m^2 which would indicate a grid size of 0.30 m. However, a grid size of 0.40 m was found to be the optimal grid size as it greatly reduced the required percentage of interpolation. For example, the interpolation in a window of a scan with good coverage (24 April 2022 at 13:40) reduced from 35% to 14% with a grid size of 0.3 and 0.4 m, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure S2.

The effect of grid size on the amount of interpolation needed for a window in the scan of 24 April 2022 at 1:40 a.m. A grid size of 0.4 m was chosen based on the decrease in interpolation between a grid size of 0.3 and 0.4 m.

